

Tarihi A Waƙe: Nazari Akan Waƙar Shahara Ta Aminu Ladan Abubakar Alan Waƙa.

Garba Lawal

Tsangayar Ilimi, Jami'ar Jihar Kaduna

Gabatarwa:

Waƙa zance ne mai tattare da hikima da tsari cikin sautin murya mai zaƙi da jan hankali wadda ake yin ta domin isar da wasu saƙonni da za su amfanar da jama'a. irin wannan saƙo shi ake kira da jigo wanda yake bijirowa ta fannoni daban-daban cikin sha'anoni da suka shafi rayuwar al'umma. Mawaƙa kuwa wasu mutane ne da Allah (SWT) yah ore masu wata baiwa ta hikimar iya sarrafa zantuka da kalmomi a waƙoƙi da nufin gargadi ko wa'azi dangane da wasu abubuwa marasa kyau da ake aikatawa, waƙanda ka iya gurbata rayuwar Jama'a. Wani lokaci kuma mawaƙan kan sarrafa zantuttuka ko kalmomi a waƙoƙinsu domin nishadantarwa ko kwarzanta wasu mutane da suka yi fice a wasu fannoni da suka shafi rayuwa ta yau da kullum. Wannan yanayi na jujjuya kalma ko sarrafa zance a waƙa shi ake kira da salo, wanda yake nufin duk wata dabara ko hanya da aka bi yayin aiwatar da waƙa domin isar da wasu saƙonni. Irin wannan dabara ta kan yi wa waƙa kwalliya ta yadda saƙon dake kunshe a waƙar zai samu isa koi tsaye ga masu saurare. Aminu Ladan Abubakar (ALA) yana daga cikin mawaƙan Hausa na zamani wanda ya shahara a fagen rera waƙoƙin Hausa da suka danganci fannonin rayuwa daban-daban, kama tun daga kan wa'azi, faɗakarwa, ilmantarwa, shugabanci da kuma waƙanda suka shafi harkokin siyasa. Maƙasudin wannan muƙala shi ne tsokaci kan yadda mawaƙin ya yi amfani da salon tarihi a waƙarsa ta shahara.

Tafaitaccen Tarihin Aminu Ladan Abubakar (ALA)

Masana da manazarta irin su Imran (2008) da Umar (2011) da Hamza (2011) da Isa (2013) da Muhammad (2014) da Yakasai da Sani (2021). Duk sun yu tarayya a kan cewa an haifi Aminu Ladan Abubakar (ALA) a ranar talata 2 ga watan 10 shekara ta 1973 cikin shekarar hijira ta 1394 a Unguwar Yakasai ƙaramar hukumar birni da kewaye, jihar Kano. Sai dai kuma an yaye shi ne a wata Unguwa ta daban, wato a unguwar Kofar Wambai a hannun kakanninsa. Daga baya sai iyayensa suka yi ƙaura zuwa ƙaramar hukumar Nasarawa inda suka zauna a unguwar Tudun Murtala.

Aminu Ladan Abubakar (ALA) ya fara karatu ne da koyon karatun addini a ƙarƙashin wani malami mai suna Malam Muhammad Sani wanda ake yi wa laƙabi da Malam Dan-Sakkwato wanda a wurinsa ne ya haddace izifi biyar daga cikin Alƙur'ani Mai Girma. Baya ga nan kuma ya yi karatu a wata makarantar Islamiyya mai suna Zaharaddeen Islamiyya ta Tudun Murtala ƙarƙashin Kulawar Malam Usman Tudun Wada, inda ya fara tun daga rabin aji har ya zuwa aji shida, wanda daga baya kuma ya zama ɗaya daga cikin Malaman Makarantar.

Aminu Ladan Abubakar (ALA) ya fara karatun boko ne a wata makarantar Firamare mai suna Tudun Murtala Primary School, inda ya yi karatu a tsakanin shekarar 1980 zuwa 1986. Daga nan kuma sai ya halarci makarantar Sakandire ta Dakata Kawaji wato (Government Senior Secondary School, Dakata Kawaji) daga shekara ta 1986 zuwa 1992. Bayan ya kammala karatunsa na Sakandire a shekara ta 1992, sai ya dakatar da ci gaba da karatu sakamakon matsaloli irin na rayuwar yau da kullum har tsawon shekaru goma sha biyu (12). Daga baya ya koma makarantar gaba da sakandire a shekara ta (2000) inda ya shiga makarantar fasaha ta Kano wato (School of technology Kano) inda ya yi karatu a fannin zane-zane wato (Department of Arts and Industrial Design) a wannan makaranta ya samu shedar Diploma ta ƙasa a shekarar 2003.

Wakar Shahara Ta Aminu Ladan Abubakara (ALA)

Wakar shahara wasu jerin waƙoƙi ne guda biyar da Aminu Ladan Abubakar (Alan Waƙa) ya rera domin bayyana tarihin rayuwarsa, dangane da abubuwan da suka shafi gwagwarmaya da kalubale da kuma yadda mawaƙin ya yi fice a duniyar waƙoƙin Hausa na zamani. Mawaƙin ya karkasa waƙoƙin rukuni-rukuni har zuwa rukuni guda biyar, a inda kowane rukuni ya raɗa masa suna dangane da yadda baitocin kowane rukuni ya kunsu wato kamar haka:

Rukunin tarihi inda mawaƙin yake bayyana tarihin rayuwarsa tun daga rana da shekarar da aka haife shi har ya zuwa karance-karancensa tare da bayyana wasu ayyukan fasaha da ya gudanar a rayuwarsa.

Tarihin Haihuwa da Salsalar Aminu Ladan Abubakar (Alan Waƙa) a Waƙar Shara

Tarihi kalma ce ta Larabci wato (tarik) wacce take nufin labarin wani abu da ya faru a baya. Mafiya yawan mutane kan kira labari a matsayin tarihi a sakamakon wani abu da ya faru kuma ya shuɗe sai dai labarinsa. Akan ɗauki wata al'umma a bayar da tarihin kafuwarta ko asalinta ko ire-iren ci gaban da ta samu a rayuwa. Haka kuma, akan bayar da tarihin rayuwar wani shahararren mutum kamar basarake ko attajiri ko ɗan kasuwa ko kuma wani wadda ya yi fice a wata harka da ta shafi rayuwar al'umma, wato kamar yadda Aminu Ladan Abubakar Alan waƙa ya yi fice a fannin rera waƙoƙin Hausa na zamani da ya ke bayyana tarihin rayuwarsa da salsalar asalinsa a cikin waƙarsa ta shahara. A inda ya bayyana sunansa na asali da sunayen kakanninsa da na iyayensa da asalin garuruwansu da shekara da kuma garin da aka haife shi da dai sauransu.

Kamar dai yadda yake ambatawa a cikin waƙar, inda ya ke cewa:

***Jagora:** Masarautar Bawa Gwarzo,
Ku ji salsalar Ubana.
Suna na Al'aminu
Da shi aka raɗɗa suna
Alhaji Ladan Ubana,
Da Abubakar kakana,
Sunan da na sawa kaina,
Alan Waƙar yabo na,
Sakan da nai yi ma sunayena,
Na cire ciki laƙƙabina,
Asali na garin ubana,
Jega Kebbi Sitet ka tona,
Asali na garin Uwana,
Dabo ta Kano garina,
Gari ko na haihuwa na,
Birni na Kano garina,
Shekarar ran haihuwana,
Kirgen shari'ar Nabina,
Aijira ta Alif dubu ɗai,
Da ɗari uku da ɗigon na,*

***Amshi:** Shahara sanadin sanina.
Sanadin Ilimi na ALA.*

***Jagora:** Ma'anar manufar jigon na,
Kirge kuma nan nasara,
Naitin sabinti tiri na,
A Munisifal Kanawa,
Yakasai ta gari na,
Nan ne aka haihuwa ta,*

*Labarin assalina,
Nai ilimin usilina,
Ma tayassara gwargwadona,
Mai ilimin zamani na,
Boko dan Zamani na,
Gwargwado dai diffuloma,
Nai domin kare kai na,
Nai kan at an dizayan,
KirKiren zane fuluna,
Duka dangogin fasaha,
Na fi karfin lammura na,
Nai rubutu nai hikoya,
Dikishin karin bayana.*

(Wakar shahara: Rukuni na daya).

Haƙika waɗannan baitoci da suka gabata na daga wannan waƙa kunshe su ke da tarihin rayuwar Aminu Ladan Abubakar Alan Waƙa kama tun daga garin haihuwa da shekara da kwanan wata da sauransu. Har wa yau kuma, mawaƙin ya bayyana matsayin karatunsa na addini da na zamani (boko). Baya ga nan kuma, mawaƙin ya kawo tarihin salsalar asalin kakanninsa da garuruwan da suka fito da na iyayensa duk a cikin wannan waƙa ta shahara, da nufin bayyana tarihin rayuwarsa.

Babu shakka ko tantama babu idan aka yi la'akari da waɗannan zantuttuka da suka gabata a cikin waɗannan baitoci na daga wannan waƙa, za a fahimci cewa babu komai a cikinsu illa tarihin rayuwar mawaƙi Aminu Ladan Abubakar (Alan Waƙa).

Tarihin Gwagwarmayar Aminu Ladan Abubakar (Alan Waƙa)

Aminu Ladan Abubakar (Alan waƙa) ya shahara a fagen shirya waƙoƙin Hausa na zamani domin kuwa ya rera waƙoƙin Hausa da dama da suka shafi rayuwar al'umma ta fuskoki daban-daban wadda hakan ya sa ya fuskanci kalubale da gwagwarmaya a tsakaninsa da sauran 'yan uwansa mawaƙan Hausa na zamani. Har wa yau kuma, mawaƙin ya fuskanci kalubale tsakaninsa da hukumar tace fina-finan Hausa ta Jihar Kano (Censorship Board) wadda hakan ya zama sanadiyyar zuwansa gidan kurkuku (Prison) kamar yadda yake bayyanawa a cikin waƙarsa. Inda yake cewa:

Jagora: *Karfe biyu cif na rana,
Jama'a sun bar gurina,
Sai ga mota ta Prison,
Da ma'aikata da rana,
Sai ga alkali ya zo,
Sai ga Lauya ya zauna,
A cikin minti kalilan,
Aka ce "mu shige, mu zauna",
Aka sake karanta kara,
Aka sake daga zamana,
Amma kuma wanga loto,
Ba beli wai a kaina,
Lauya ya bukaci beli,
Aka ce "Ba beli a kaina",
Jami'ai suka sani mota,
Sai kurkuku zani kwana,
Abun al'ajabbi da ya,
Dumana mani kaina,
Da isar mu gida na jarum,*

*Jama'a na ta tsumina,
Amshi: Shahara ce dan mabudfin,
 Ilimi aka san sanina.
Jagora: Aka bude mani kofa,
 Da shiga na dagga kaina,
 Na ji ihu ya karade,
 Ya juyan hankali na,
 Ihun da akai a loton,
 Ya rudan kunnuwa na,
 Take sai suka fara
 Wakar bakan dabin garina,
 Yin hakan da sukai gareni,
 Sai ya juyan hankali na,
 Sai na ma rasa inda zani,
 Sai na nemi guri na zauna,
 Jami'an doka na Prison,
 Suka harhana tsokana na,
 Suka ce "Zo nan cikinmu
 Mu yi Sallah sai mu zauna",
 Da muka gama alwalarmu,
 Ni nai Liman da kai na,
 Ni idar kuma nai du'a'i,
 Jarabawa yau a kaina.*

(Wakar Shahara rukuni na Huɗu).

Duk wadannan baitoci da suka gabata na daga wannan waƙa kunshe suke da bayanan tarihin gwagwarmaya da kalubale waɗanda mawaƙin ya fuskanta a rayuwa da suka zama sanadiyyar zuwansa gidan kurkuku (prison) sakamakon taƙaddama da rashin fahimta da ya shiga tsakaninsa da hukumar tace fina-finan Hausa na Jihar Kano (Censorship Board) a dalilin shirya waƙa da ta saba dokar jihar Kano da kuma hukumar tace fina-finan Hausa. Da wannan Aminu Ladan Abubakar (Alan Waƙa) yake bayyana abubuwan da suka faru a baya da suka yi sanadiyyar zuwansa gidan kurkuku (prison), wadda hakan yana ɗaya daga cikin samun ɗaukaka da sharar mawaƙin a fagen waƙoƙin Hausa na zamani.

Kammalawa

Haƙiƙa waƙar shahara, ta Aminu Ladan Abubakar (Alan Waƙa) waƙa ce da take kunshe da tarihi, wato inda mawaƙin yake bayyana labarin rayuwarsa tun daga ranar haihuwa da gari da kuma matsayin karatunsa na addini da na zamani. Sai kuma labarin gwagwarmaya da kalubalen da mawaƙin ya fuskanta a rayuwa. Wannan wani nau'in salo ne da ba a saba ganinsa ba a fagen shirya waƙoƙin Hausa, da wannan muƙala ta nazarta domin gano manufa ko hikimar mawaƙin ta yin amfani da irin wannan salon a bayyana tarihi a waƙe. da wannan ake ganin cewa mawaƙin ya yi amfani da wannan salo ne domin ganin ya saukaƙa wa jama'a musamman ga masoya waƙoƙinsa wajen samun tarihin rayuwarsa a cikin sauƙi tare da sanin gwagwarmaya da kuma kalubalen da ya fuskanta a rayuwarsa. Har wa yau kuma waƙar shekara za ta taimaka matuƙa ga 'yan uwa ɗalibai da sauran manazarta wajen samun tarihin rayuwan mawaƙin cikin sauƙi ba tare da sun wahala ba.

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